

Molecular Characteristics and Ultrasonic Degradation of Neoprene AD*

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The results of ultrasonic degradation and molecular characteristics of Neoprene AD are described. There is a wide distribution of molecular weight ($0.52 - 33.86 \times 10^5$) in Neoprene AD and after fractionation, the higher molecular weight fractions form gels probably due to the formation of readily crystallizable or cross linked products. In sol fractions, the root mean square end-to-end distances, ($\langle r^2 \rangle_z$)^{1/2} of coiled molecules vary regularly in the same direction as the weight average molecular weight. The intrinsic viscosity-molecular weight relationship in two solvents, chloroform and toluene, at 30° has been determined. The study of ultrasonic degradation of Neoprene AD in toluene has shown that the behaviour of this rubber is rather different from that of butyl rubber, a structurally irregular polymer. Unlike butyl rubber, the degradation rates, as obtained by the two methods—solution viscosity and free radical estimation as a function of DPPH consumed, are more or less the same. The rate of degradation for Neoprene AD (trans rubber) is 1.6 times more than that of natural rubber (cis rubber). A possible explanation for this has been given.

On a programme in this laboratory for studying the ultrasonic degradation of some industrially useful polymers, sol rubber and butyl rubber were studied earlier¹⁻³. The work has been extended to Neoprene AD, a trans rubber, structurally different from the two earlier studied polymers. Neoprene AD is a rapidly crystallizing polymer and does not contain thiuram disulphide. Chemically speaking this is similar to the W type. The degradation rate was followed, as was done previously, using the solution viscosity method as well as the free radical estimation as a function of $\alpha\alpha'$ -diphenyl β -picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) consumed. However, for kinetic analysis by the former method, a previous knowledge of the relationship between molecular weight and viscosity for Neoprene AD in different solvents is necessary. For this reason, a sample was fractionated and the molecular weight of different fractions was determined by the light scattering method. In the course of this work, however, molecular parameters of Neoprene AD such as second virial coefficient, root mean square end-to-end distance of chains, radius of gyration, and Flory's universal constant in chloroform solution were determined. In the present paper, the results of ultrasonic degradation and molecular characteristics of Neoprene AD have been reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fractionation of Neoprene AD :

Neoprene AD sample was fractionated from a 2 percent benzene solution with slow addition of acetone by the conventional partial precipitation method. The broader fractions were redissolved while wet and fractionated in the similar way into nine fractions.

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The samples thus obtained were denoted by 1F-1, 1F-2, 1F-3, 1F-4, 1F-5, 1F-6, 1F-7, 1F-8 and 1F-9. They were dried in *vacuo* to constant weight and stored under nitrogen atmosphere.

Since the first two fractions after drying formed gel-like materials probably due to crystallization or cross-linked structure, these could not be used for molecular weight determination and degradation study. For light scattering measurements in chloroform, the polymer was fractionated from chloroform solution adding ether as nonsolvent. Each fraction was redissolved separately in pure solvent while wet and the last traces of nonsolvent (ether) was removed by distilling out the solvent-nonsolvent azeotrope under reduced pressure several times until zero reading for distillate was observed in a differential refractometer. Only first two fractions, 2F-1 and 2F-2, from this batch were used.

For degradation studies on the sample having highest molecular weight, in toluene the original polymer was fractionated once again into several fractions from toluene solution using acetone as nonsolvent and only the first fraction, 3F-1 was recovered. The last traces of nonsolvent from this fraction was removed in the similar way as indicated above.

Viscosity measurements :

The viscosity of the solutions were measured with a Ubbelohde dilution viscometer thermostated at $30 \pm 0.02^\circ$. The intrinsic viscosity was obtained by extrapolation of plots of the reduced viscosity, η_{sp}/c versus concentration to infinite dilution.

Light Scattering Measurements :

Light scattering measurements were carried out in a Brice-Phonex photometer using cylindrical cell with plane windows. Measurements were made on solution for five different concentrations at different angles covering the range 35° to 135° . Unpolarized blue light ($\lambda = 4360 \text{ \AA}$) was used for all measurements. The solvent, chloroform, was carefully distilled in all-glass apparatus till it did not show any dissymmetry. The solutions were clarified by positive pressure filtration in a closed vessel through sintered glass ultrafine filters (Nos. 3 and 4 in succession). The refractive index gradient, dn/dc was determined with Rayleigh interference differential refractometer (Hilger Watts, England) calibrated with an aqueous sodium chloride solution at room temperature. Toluene was found unsuitable as solvent for the present light scattering study as the value of dn/dc was negligibly small. However, the value of dn/dc in chloroform solution was found to be 0.121 ml/gm .

Experimentally determined quantities were Rayleigh ratios, R_θ evaluated from the galvanometer deflections, dn/dc , refractive index of the solvent and wave length. The data were plotted as Kc/R_θ versus $\text{Sin}^2(\theta/2) + 100c$ and extrapolated to curves $\theta = 0$ and $c = 0$ in the manner proposed by Zimm. Both the constant angle and constant concentration plots were linear within the limits of experimental error.

Degradation by Ultrasonics :

Three samples of Neoprene AD in toluene were used for degradation study. A Mullard ultrasonic generator (type 7562) with 500 kc/sec quartz transducer was employed as an irradiation source. The experimental procedure has been described earlier³. The

spectrophotometric measurements were carried out in a Spektromom 201 spectrophotometer (Hungarian) and the intrinsic viscosity of the degraded sample was determined by a single point measurement using the relation given by Naar *et al.*⁴

$$[\eta] = (1/c) \sqrt{2(\eta_{sp} - \ln \eta_{rel})}$$

The viscosity average molecular weight obtained by the Mark-Houwink relation, was changed into a number average value by the relation

$$\left[\frac{(\overline{DP})\eta}{(\overline{DP})_n} \right]^a = \frac{\{\Gamma(3+a)\}}{2(1+a)} \quad (1)$$

where Γ is a gamma function and a is the exponent in Mark-Houwink equation. The number B_t of bonds broken in time t was calculated by the relation

$$(\overline{DP})_t = (\overline{DP})_0 n_0 / (n_0 + B_t) \quad (2)$$

where n_0 is the number of molecules present initially per gram of polymer having number average degree of polymerization $(\overline{DP})_0$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Molecular dimensions

Table I lists the light scattering data for Neoprene AD in chloroform together with the universal constant⁵ ϕ given by $\phi = [\eta]M/(\bar{r}^2)^{3/2}$, where $[\eta]$ is the intrinsic viscosity in the same solvent. The \bar{M}_w , Z -average dimension and second virial coefficient B are calculated from the following equations:

$$\bar{M}_w = \frac{1}{(Kc/R)_{\theta=0}}$$

$$c=0$$

$$\langle \bar{r}^2 \rangle_z = \frac{9\lambda'^2 (\text{slope of the line } c=0)}{8\pi^2 (\text{intercept})}$$

where λ' is the wave length of light in chloroform and is equal to 4360/1.44643 or 3014.32 Å and $2B$ equals the slope of the line $\theta = 0$.

After separation of the first two fractions (gel forming fractions), the Zimm diagram for the remaining seven fractions (sol fractions) were quite regular showing none of the distortions usually displayed by gel fractions or unfractionated sample. The typical Zimm diagram for sol fraction (1F-5) together with the unfractionated sample are shown in figure 1. The first two fractions (2F-1 and 2F-2) had developed slight turbidities during the process

4. R. Z. Naar, H. H. Zabusky and R. F. Hoitmiller, *J. Appl. Polymer Sci.*, 1963, **7**, S30.

5. T. G. Fox and P. J. Flory, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1904.

Figure 1. The typical Zimm diagrams for fraction 1F-5 and unfractionated Neoprene AD.

of removing the last traces of nonsolvent and the turbidities were not cleared completely even by filtration with ultra filters. The high molecular weight (~ 2.5 times higher than viscosity average molecular weight) thus obtained for these fractions from the Zimm diagram may be partly due to this reason. For unfractionated sample, the molecular weight obtained by light scattering measurement (17.86×10^5) is about 1.87 times higher than that obtained by the viscosity average value (9.53×10^5). Strictly speaking the $[\eta]-\bar{M}_v$ relationship (details

Figure 2. Log-log plots of $[\eta]$ versus molecular weight.

given later) is valid only for sol fractions and the viscosity average molecular weight obtained with this relationship for unfractionated sample or gel fractions is approximate. It may be that some crystalline material of the first two fractions, present in unfractionated sample, enhanced the values of the light scattering data. As the solid polymer was readily soluble

in toluene or chloroform, it is assumed that initially the polymer did not contain much crystalline or crosslinked components. The formation of such materials might have taken place during preparative stages. However, it is uncertain whether the crystallization has affected the phase separation also.

TABLE 1
Properties of Neoprene AD in chloroform

$$K = 2.774 \times 10^{-7} \quad dn/dc = 0.121$$

Fraction	$10^{-5} \bar{M}_w$ in chloroform	$10^4 B$ (cc mole/ gm ²)	$(\langle r^2 \rangle_z)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Å)	$\langle S^2 \rangle_z \times 10^{-6}$ (Å ²)	$10^{-21} \phi$	$[\eta]$ chloroform (dl/gm)	$[\eta]$ toluene (dl/gm)
3F-1	33.86 ^a	—	—	—	—	—	3.95
2F-2	23.13 ^a	—	—	—	—	3.60	—
1F-3	12.50	5.76	2177	0.7898	0.286	2.36	2.25
1F-4	7.69	4.40	1640	0.4481	0.329	1.89	1.635
1F-5	5.00	7.20	1439	0.3451	0.260	1.55	1.36
1F-6	2.63	5.95	1079	0.1940	0.246	1.175	0.975
1F-7	1.92	6.00	829	0.1145	0.330	0.98	—
1F-8	1.57	7.26	775	0.1001	0.287	0.85	0.75
1F-9	0.521	—	—	—	—	0.39	0.36
Unfracn. sample	17.86 9.53 ^a	2.17	1751	0.5110	0.6458	2.20	1.94

^a Viscosity average molecular weight.

As expected, the root mean square end-to-end distance, $(\langle r^2 \rangle_z)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ of the coil (Table 1, column 4) molecules varied regularly in the same direction as that of the weight average molecular weight.

The average value of ϕ as obtained for sol fractions is found to be 0.29×10^{21} which is appreciably lower than the theoretical value $2.1 \pm 0.3 \times 10^{21}$. However lower values are observed due to non-homogeneity of a sample as well as due to the non-ideality of the solution. Newman *et al.*⁶ have incorporated a quantity q (a measure of nonhomogeneity) to the Flory-Fox equation as $\phi = q[\eta] \bar{M}_w / (\langle \bar{r}^2 \rangle_z)^{3/2}$ to simplify the determination of ϕ from viscosity and light scattering data while preserving the correct method of averaging. Comparing the theoretical to the experimental (uncorrected) value of ϕ , the value of q works out to be 7.25 which is not due to residual heterogeneity of the sample.

Relationship between molecular weight and intrinsic viscosity :

The relationship between intrinsic viscosity and molecular weight for Neoprene AD has been determined by the Mark-Houwink equation

$$[\eta] = K \bar{M}_v^a$$

A set of constants K and a for each solvent at 30° has been evaluated by comparing $[\eta]$ of seven fractions with their molecular weight determined in chloroform solution by the light scattering method. The results of $[\eta]$ and \overline{M}_w for a number of fractions as listed in Table 1 are shown in log-log plots in Figure 2. The straight lines drawn through these points are computed by the least square method and the constants K and a have been evaluated from intercepts and slopes of the lines. The intrinsic viscosity-molecular weight relationships thus obtained are as

$$[\eta] = 10.90 \times 10^{-4} \overline{M}_w^{0.5525} \quad \text{in chloroform at } 30^\circ$$

$$[\eta] = 8.565 \times 10^{-4} \overline{M}_w^{0.5611} \quad \text{in toluene at } 30^\circ.$$

The values of K and a obtained for the two solvents are very close to each other. However, the magnitude of a may be taken as an indication of the solvent power as reflected by the shape of the molecules in solution, this being the highest for the thermodynamically good solvent. The values of a obtained in two solvents, chloroform and toluene, as 0.55 and 0.56 respectively clearly suggest that both the solvents were poor. Further, even though the exponents are slightly high, the relations conform closely with the ideal solvent relation $[\eta] = K\overline{M}_w^{0.50}$.

Ultrasonic Degradation ;

The results of ultrasonic degradation for three samples of Neoprene AD (DP = 5647, 14120 and 38238) in toluene at different concentrations are shown in figure 3. Experimentally

Figure 3. Rate of degradation of Neoprene AD in toluene.

determined values of B_t as a function of DPPH consumed and solution viscosity are plotted on the same graph. The corresponding plots of $(\overline{DP})_t$ versus t are shown in figures 4 and 5. $(\overline{DP})_t$ values have been calculated from the number B_t of bonds broken determined experimentally from DPPH consumption by means of the relationship given in (2). The same was also obtained from the viscosity data using equation (1). The general shape of the

Figure 4. $(\overline{DP})_t$ vs. t (DPPH consumption method).

Figure 5. $(\overline{DP})_t$ vs. t (Solution viscosity method).

rate curves obtained by the two methods of measurements is similar but not identical. From the experimental data suitable values for limiting degree of polymerization, P_e and kinetic rate constant K were chosen and B_t was calculated by the two equations given independently by Ovenall *et al.*⁷ and by Jellinek and White⁸. The details of the experimental data and degradation parameters are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Degradation parameters for Neoprene AD in toluene

Frac- tion	Conc. (gm/dl)	$10^{-18}n_0$	P_e		$(\overline{DP})_\infty$			$K \times 10^6 \text{ min}^{-1}$			
			DPPH	Vis- cosity	DPPH	Vis- cosity	DPPH	Vis- cosity	Ovenall <i>et al.</i>		Jellinek and White
3F-1	0.05	0.2057	2720	3230	38,238	2200	2800	4.4	2.7	2.75	1.7
3F-1	0.10	0.2057	3080	4240	38,238	2600	3900	3.5	2.4	2.0	1.3
1F-3	0.10	0.4818	2860	4040	14,120	2500	4000	3.2	2.2	1.6	1.1
1F-5	0.10	1.2050	3100	2610	5,647	2800	2600	2.8	3.0	1.2	1.5
Butyl rubber ^a	0.10	0.4459	2163	7397	23,986	1900	6300	5.5	1.5	3.2	0.8
Natural rubber ^a	0.075	0.2069	2520	—	42,390	2200	—	2.5	—	2.0	—

^a Data from Chandra *et al.*³

It is observed from the table that the rates obtained by DPPH estimation method are slightly higher (~ 1.5 times) than that by solution viscosity measurements. Accordingly the values of P_e and $(\overline{DP})_\infty$ obtained by solution viscosity measurements are little higher than that obtained by DPPH estimation. However, in case of lowest fraction ($DP = 5647$), the rates obtained by the two methods are almost equal (rather the rate by DPPH estimation is found slightly lower than that of the rate by viscosity measurement). It is interesting to note that in butyl rubber degradation, the rates obtained by the two methods were widely different (~ 4 times) and so also were the values of P_e and $(\overline{DP})_\infty$. The degradation behaviour of Neoprene AD is rather different from that of butyl rubber (structurally very irregular).

Further it is observed that the degradation rate for Neoprene AD ($K = \sim 4.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for 0.075% solution of 3F-1) is about 1.6 times higher than that of natural rubber (cis). To explain this it may be said that the trans polymer is not so elastic (rigidity is relatively high) and this may break more easily if the distorting force is high enough whereas in case of cis polymer due to its flexibility can resist this disruptive force by assuming suitable conformation.

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